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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Retraining-Free Pruning Text-to-Speech Synthesis Model for Speaker Cloning

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ABSTRACT End-to-end text-to-speech (TTS) synthesis models can produce highly natural speech by drawing on large-scale pretraining with extensive datasets and subsequent adaptation to specific target speakers, such as voice cloning. However, as model sizes grow with increasingly comprehensive pretraining, fine-tuning all parameters for each speaker becomes both computationally demanding and resource-intensive. In this study, we adapted Pruning by Weights and Activations (Wanda), a technique initially developed for large language models, to reduce the parameter footprint of pretrained TTS models for voice cloning. Wanda leverages a simple yet effective metric to prune redundant parameters by multiplying weight magnitudes by input activation norms. It does not require post-retraining to preserve the synthesized speech quality and allows for efficient adaptation to cloned voices. Our proposed pruning TTS method uses two pruning schemes, *structured Wanda* (removes all units, such as neurons, filters, or channels) and *unstructured Wanda* (removes weights or individual connections based on magnitude or significance scores). Subjective and objective evaluations showed that the pruned TTS model exhibited promising results and was comparable to the baseline TTS model (non-pruned) at the one-quarter pruning level. Our proposed pruned TTS model subjectively achieved only a relatively small decline in naturalness of approximately 4.3% in a sparsity of one-quarter with the structured Wanda and 23% in moderate pruning levels of one-half using the unstructured Wanda. The findings demonstrate that our approach yields lightweight TTS models deployed efficiently to address the scalability challenges in modern speech synthesis systems. The outcome of this study supports the development of personalized TTS systems with potential applications for communication aids for individuals with speech disorders.

INDEX TERMS Efficient inference, model compression, pruning, speaker adaptation, text-to-speech synthesis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Text-to-speech (TTS) synthesis has seen remarkable improvements driven by expanding deep learning approaches. High-quality, natural-sounding speech synthesis is increasingly requested across diverse applications, from virtual

assistants and accessibility tools to audiobooks and interactive gaming. However, the computational demand for high-resolution speech remains a significant challenge, especially when integrating these models into resource-limited devices, such as smartphones, IoT devices, and embedded systems. Neural TTS models, which are over-parameterized architectures, need significant computational costs and substantial memory resources [1], [2].

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